

THE DEVELOPMENT OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEXICAL COMPETENCE BASED ON WORKING WITH A DICTIONARY FOR FUTURE ENGLISH TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15545519>

***Abstract.** This article is about the development of foreign language lexical competence based on working with a dictionary for future English teachers. The level of formation of lexical competence is an important indicator in the development of communicative competence in a foreign language of future English teachers.*

***Keywords.** Lexical competence, lexis, competence, passive lexical reserve, terminology.*

The main content of the development of educational-lexical competencies in future English teachers involves the development and improvement of skills in independently mastering and applying lexical units in a foreign language in practice. This competency includes skills such as understanding the content of the text through the effective use of foreign language dictionaries, mastering new lexical units based on context, as well as the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in various communicative situations. In this process, the main attention is paid to the issues of systematically organizing the linguistic and cognitive activities of future foreign language teachers through working with dictionaries, expanding their vocabulary, and qualitatively improving their speech activity.

The work carried out on the development and improvement of foreign language-lexical competencies in future English teachers, proceeding from a linguodidactic point of view, increases the ability of teachers to successfully perform the communicative tasks necessary in their future pedagogical activities. This competency development methodology involves teaching students to understand foreign language texts in a deep and conscious way through working with a dictionary, and on this basis, developing skills in the effective use of foreign language dictionaries.

An analysis of existing research in the field of educational lexicography shows that, although scientists have tried to activate students' cognitive activity, they are still scattered and have not developed a common, unified theoretical framework that fully meets the requirements of the competency-based approach. The role and importance of the development of educational-lexical competence in future English teachers in the professional competence of a foreign language teacher require the presence of a common methodological basis in this area - a programmatic and practical basis for creating an educational-lexicon. As such a basis, we indicate a set of educational and cognitive actions that should be carried out by students and lead to the development of the necessary competencies.

Within the framework of the studied situation, the stage of developing motives is manifested in a shortened form, since the motive often arises in the process of working with the text - when encountering an unfamiliar word, and the student, as a rule, resorts to working with a dictionary without external incentives. In our study, the task of this stage in the independent mastering of a foreign language dictionary is, first of all, to develop positive motivation by

overcoming motivational barriers and negative psychological states, combining them with appropriate motivating factors and successful results.

One of the first linguists, who tried to describe what it means to ‘know a word’, was J. Richards [1; P.54]. According to him, knowing a word isn’t limited to the knowledge of its meanings and word forms, its derivatives, but also includes the knowledge of its syntactic behavior and the net of associations of the word with other words. He notes that the bigger the vocabulary size is, the higher the significance of the system of relations and associations between words.

As a means of developing educational and lexical competencies, it is necessary to develop knowledge in future English teachers about methods of overcoming motivational barriers that arise in the process of working with the dictionary and strengthening positive motivation. This stage of this process is closely related to the student's experience of emotional and value relations with real reality.

□ The process of developing educational and cognitive skills related to the acquisition of foreign language vocabulary in the activity of developing direction and purpose is the main condition for the development of educational and lexical competencies in future English teachers. Because purposefulness is considered one of the most important features of human activity. According to B.F. Lomov [5; P.87], there is no activity without a goal or without action. Motive and goal are a kind of "vector" that determines the direction of activity, and at the same time determines the amount of effort and energy expended by the subject to implement it. This vector is the main component of the system of all mental processes and states that develop and arise during activity.

The effectiveness of educational activities, according to I.S. Yakimanskaya [9; P.76], in the process of developing the educational and lexical competencies of future English teachers, represents the individual selectivity of the student in mastering educational material of various scientific content, forms and types, stable preferences and opportunities for effective use of the acquired knowledge. The generally mastered methods of educational activity gradually turn into individual ways of activity. As a result, the development of students is ensured through the enrichment of personal experience and the development of educational and lexical competencies of future English teachers.

Table 1.3

Forms of working with a dictionary

1	determining the program components of lexical units that need to be independently mastered, the set of learning actions and communicative methods that correspond to the adopted goals, and their sequence;
2	organizational and planning actions in the process of mastering a foreign language vocabulary;
3	determining a convenient time and place for mastering a foreign language vocabulary, selecting a dictionary and educational materials and determining their volume;
4	consolidating the mastered lexical units by performing practical communicative tasks (for example, actively using new words in the process of reading a text or scientific articles);

5	identifying vocabulary combinations necessary for future communicative tasks and a deep understanding of the content of the text;
6	performing actions such as recalling lexical units from memory or remembering them in an automated manner during the performance of speech acts, selecting the words necessary in the process of preparing speech statements, identifying and effectively using important lexical units in the text in the process of performing various communicative tasks.

To develop the skills of this stage, it is also necessary to develop the appropriate knowledge about the means and methods of achieving goals in working with a dictionary and programming methods in the process of developing the educational and lexical competencies of future English teachers. In the process of developing educational and cognitive skills related to mastering a foreign language vocabulary at the implementation stage, the development of educational and lexical competencies of future English teachers should be carried out in two ways, as in the previous stages. On the one hand, working with a dictionary should provide students with the necessary subject knowledge about the lexical unit being mastered (subject knowledge), and also regularly update the knowledge of future English teachers about the techniques for developing educational and lexical competencies (information about the techniques for obtaining and using lexical units).

On the other hand, through the implementation of appropriate educational activities, students should serve as a means of developing and developing their subject-lexical skills (skills for mastering lexical knowledge and applying it in practice). Below we identify a set of automatic-methodical and subject-oriented educational-cognitive actions that serve to master and develop these knowledge and skills:

Precise development of the dictionary program and the methods and tools used in it, as well as programming individual work on the dictionary; – Choosing a technique for mastering lexical units and independently selecting and effectively using the necessary tools (dictionaries, electronic platforms, mobile applications, etc.) in the process of mastering them; – Drawing up a general plan for working with lexical units, determining the time and sequence of activities for working with the dictionary, increasing personal responsibility for following these plans;

– Strengthening the lexical units studied on the topic by effectively and consciously using them in communication situations and developing practical speech experience; – Identifying new lexical units in the process of reading various texts (scientific, professional, artistic), mastering and strengthening their semantic and functional properties based on the context;

– Using lexical units in memory automatically in the process of performing speech situations and communicative tasks, and using strategies to reactivate and strengthen lexical knowledge in one's memory if necessary;

– Independently identify the causes of failure in the application of lexical knowledge and develop methods for their operational elimination.

Thus, the above set of automatic-methodical and subject-oriented educational-cognitive actions is the main tool that must be effectively and systematically used in the process of developing foreign language lexical competencies of future English teachers.

A special complex of exercises for developing foreign language lexical skills and speech abilities (informative reading, monological speaking) was developed. This complex is

based on four interrelated stages of lexical skills and speech abilities development: 1) semantization and reproduction of lexical means; 2) stereotyping and varying of lexical means; 3) systematic

application of FL lexical skills, their dynamic integration with other speech skills during oral and written communication; 4) synthesis and systematization of FL lexical skills at the stage of development of creative speech abilities [2; P. 121-122].

The activity of perceiving (perceiving and understanding) the form and content of semantically unfamiliar lexical units is of great importance in the process of developing educational and lexical competencies in future English teachers. The main task of this stage is to develop skills that allow students to effectively perceive, organize and store lexical information in long-term memory when working with a dictionary. The effectiveness of developing these skills largely depends on the volume of semantic knowledge (lexical information) about foreign words being mastered by students and their conscious use, which ensures quick and high-quality understanding of words in texts and their conscious use.

The synthesis of automatic-methodical and subject-specific knowledge and skills in the activity of perceiving foreign lexis and understanding its semantics allowed us to identify a set of certain actions. Their regular implementation creates the opportunity to effectively develop students' skills in working with a dictionary.

In the educational situation we are studying, the acquisition of a new lexical unit begins with its perception in the process of working on the educational text. The educational and cognitive actions that students need to perform at this stage are the following:

– starting to independently search for new lexical units within a specific context based on the educational task or personal communicative need;

– perceiving the form of a new lexical unit, recording it in the sensory register, and at the same time consciously realizing the need to understand its content by paying attention to the main features (signs) of the perceived lexical information.

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